

GERMPLASM IMPROVEMENT

Genetic resources

Some restorers and maintainers of WA cyto-sterile lines

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Using Chinese CMS line V20A as a common female parent, eight crosses with standard rice cultivars were made during 1984 wet season. To identify restorers and maintainers, 20 plants from each hybrid and the male parents

grown in the test cross nursery in 1985 were examined for pollen fertility and spikelet seed-setting percentage. Male parents of the F_1 that showed 70-80% pollen fertility and above 80% spikelet fertility were designated restorers. Male parents of the F_1 showing 5-7% pollen fertility were designated maintainers. Male parents showing intermediate pollen and spikelet fertility were designated partial restorers.

IR54, BIET8549, BIET1009, and Radha were identified as restorers, Br. 9 and Cuttack Basmati as partial

Spikelet and pollen fertility percentages in F_1 hybrids and their male parents.

Cross and male parent	Spikelet fertility (%)	Pollen fertility (%)
V20A/IR54	85.8	76
IR54	86.9	80
V20A/Br. 34	12.2	7
Br. 34	89.1	79
V20A/Br. 9	29.0	16
Br. 9	83.0	76
V20A/Cuttack Basmati	39.0	23
Cuttack Basmati	91.2	88
V20A/BIET8549	82.5	71
BIET8549	89.1	74
V20A/BIET1009	86.8	81
BIET1009	89.2	81
V20A/Radha	84.9	76
Radha	91.0	89
V20A/BIET8550	10.5	6
BIET8550	85.5	76

restorers, and Br. 34 and BIET8550 as maintainers (see table). □

Breeding methods

Rice dwarf mutant of Seratus Malam variety

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Seeds of Seratus Malam, a local upland rice variety (tall with long panicles and high yielding potential) were irradiated

Agronomic characters of dwarf mutant M-362 and the mother variety Seratus Malam.

Characteristic	Mutant M-362	Seratus Malam
Plant height (cm)	58.50	119.00
Productive tillers (no.)	4.50	10.00
Panicle length (cm)	17.17	27.00
Culm length (cm)	41.33	92.00
1,000-grain weight (g)	12.75	22.24
Yield per plant (g)	10.55	18.41

with gamma rays at 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4 and 0.5 kGy in 1983. Plants were selected in the M_2 generation for dwarf and semidwarf stature.

From 50,000 M_2 plants, 130 semidwarf mutants and 1 dwarf mutant were selected. Dwarf mutant M-362 was isolated from the 0.1 kGy gamma ray treatment. It has significantly shorter plants, shorter culms, lower number of productive tillers, shorter panicles, and lower 1,000-grain weight than Seratus Malam (see table).

In the allelic test, dwarf mutant M-362 was crossed with Acc. 123 (carrying DGWG gene). Dwarf mutant M-362 was not allelic with Acc. 123.

Performance of dwarf mutant M-362 is shown in the figure. □

Stature of M-362 dwarf mutant and the mother variety Seratus Malam. Jakarta, Indonesia.

Seratus Malam

Dwarf mutant

Effects of antimutagenic agents on growth and differentiation of rice tissues grown *in vitro*

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We studied the effects of three antimutagenic agents — chloral hydrate,

p-fluorophenylalanine (FPA), and ethionine — on growth and differentiation of cultured explants (root, shoot, endosperm, and embryo) of indica rice varieties Sita and Rajendra Dhan 201. All the chemicals decreased the rate of elongation of roots and shoots differentiated from treated embryos and fresh and dry weights of root, shoot, and endosperm calli. The extent of growth inhibition depended on the chemical and its concentration. Of the three, ethionine was most effective.

The morphological changes induced by the chemicals were manifested at the macromolecular levels as well. They lowered the levels of DNA, protein, and carbohydrates of the plantlets differentiated from chemically treated embryos, thereby indicating an overall disturbance in general metabolism (see table).

The decrease in the amount of total DNA gives indirect evidence for the changes induced in the levels of ploidy

Effects of antimetabolites on DNA, protein, and carbohydrate contents of 10-day-old plantlets differentiated from excised embryos.

Chemical	Concentration (mg/liter)	Amount in µg/g fresh weight of plantlets		
		DNA	Protein	Carbohydrate
Control	0.0	1060.0 ±44.9	417.6 ±28.4	544.3 ±21.1
Chloral hydrate	82.7	534.2 ±31.4	198.0 ±28.3	259.6 ±21.8
	165.4	237.4 ±31.1	130.3 ±2.8	150.7 ±10.8
	827.0	204.6 ±52.6	113.2 ±14.2	141.5 ±3.0
FPA	25.0	973.0 ±25.9	273.9 ±17.8	228.6 ±13.1
	50.0	789.7 ±57.1	176.2 ±28.1	187.2 ±3.8
	100.0	463.2 ±55.8	141.7 ±20.4	149.7 ±6.7
Ethionine	5.0	735.6 ±69.4	311.9 ±16.5	345.6 ±25.2
	10.0	295.7 ±32.3	163.7 ±40.2	317.8 ±15.8
	15.0	253.0 ±8.8	129.4 ±16.2	296.6 ±2.3

of the treated tissues. Cytological studies of the treated tissues are needed to reveal the nature of permanent heritable

changes brought about by these antimetabolites. □

Yield potential

Performance of japonica/indica cross derivatives under rainfed upland conditions

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Pre-wet season rainfed rice is grown in about 336.4 thousand ha in northern West Bengal. Rainfall varies from 4,000 mm at Cooch-behar to 1,430 mm at Malda; 80% falls between May and Sep. Drought is not common in Cooch-behar, Jalpaiguri, and Darjeeling districts, but happens occasionally in West Dinajpur and Malda. Germination and initial growth of the crop direct seeded early Mar in the terai region of Jalpaiguri and Cooch-behar is affected by low temperature (17-20 °C). Growth of the crop seeded late Apr and

May in West Dinajpur and Malda is affected by high temperature (around 40 °C).

The problems associated with prekharif yields include unevenly occurring drought spells; soil deficiencies, mostly N and P; diseases,

mostly blast, sheath rot, and brown spot; insects, termites, stem borers, mealybug, and leafhoppers; and root-knot nematodes. Weeds also are an important problem.

We screened 37 F₄ bulk population crosses including japonicas and indicas from IRRI and local cultivars at Malda in prekharif 1986. Seeds were sown in

Table 1. Screening F₄ bulk crosses under rainfed upland conditions. Malda, India, 1986.

Designation	Cross	Varietal group ^a	Panicle length (cm)	Duration (d)	Fertile grains (no./panicle)	Grain fertility (%)	Selections made (no.)
IR47724-14	Moroberekan/IRAT177	VI/VI	16-25	90	50-140	12-47	5
IR47730-4	IRAT112/Apura	VI/I	15-23	81-92	42-92	0-60	23
IR47705-6	Moroberekan/Palawan	VI/VI	15-20	88-90	52-100	10-71	10
IR47697-2	ITA235/IR9669 sel.	VI/I	15-20	90-92	54-85	32-70	8
IR47688-35	IRAT112/Sein Talay	VI/I	15-22	90-91	79-102	45-50	3
IR47687-10	IRAT104/Salumpikit	VI/I	16-19	91-94	80-135	0-72	5
IR47699-28	IRAT104/Palawan	VI/VI	15-17	89	80-115	39-55	2
IR4768-33	IRAT104/Salumpikit	VI/I	13-18	91-93	46-68	37-38	2
IR47721-21	IRAT177/H.T. Boewani	VI/I	15-22	89	70-113	12-55	8
IR47701-20	ITA235/UPLRi 7	VI/I	17-21	80	78-94	63-65	2
IR47699-22	ITA235/Palawan	VI/VI	19-24	81-93	65-140	39-67	5
Dular	Local check		20	85	81	32	
Panke	Local check		23	100	123	9	
Soni	Local check		19	82	65	43	

^aI = indica, VI = japonica.